

Technical and Policy Mechanisms to Mitigate Interference and Contamination in Lunar Operations T. Jones¹, A. Chronopoulos¹, L. Petzold¹, S. Schubert¹, E. Shashkova¹. ¹European Space Policy Institute (Schwarzenbergplatz 16/Top 1, 1010 Vienna, Austria, therese.jones@espi.eu).

Introduction: T. Jones et al. 2025 [1] surveyed the lunar community to determine the breadth of interference and contamination concerns during lunar operations, identified information-sharing needed to evaluate the potential for interference/contamination, and the knowledge gaps in measurements, models, best practices related to interference and contamination. This work explored interference in five major categories: physical contact, thermal/optical disturbance, electromagnetic/radiofrequency interference, contamination, and seismic, and the spatiotemporal extent of the impact of these types of interference. This presentation gives an overview of the work of Jones et al. 2025, and builds upon it by examining lunar governance futures (e.g., government-dominated lunar activity, government coalition or public-private coalition-led activity, commercially-led activity) and potential technical and policy mechanisms to address coordination needs for each respective future scenario. Scientific and technical data-sharing will be critical in determining the extent of interference and contamination, while immediate interference concerns, particularly those surrounding astronaut operations on the lunar surface, will likely require more structured diplomatic channels to resolve. We map the current set of primary organizations involved in mitigation of lunar interference, and assess the channels which may be most effective for interference mitigation in the future.

Discussion: The ability to effectively address interference in lunar activities is strongly dependent on multilateral engagement of lunar actors. Today, engagement on lunar interference occurs in the following fora: the U.N. Committee on the Peaceful Uses of Outer Space (Action Team on Lunar Activities Consultation and Working Group on Space Resources); at the International Telecommunications Union (ITU); at the Committee on Space Research (COSPAR); within interagency coordination groups such as the Interagency Operations Advisory Group (IOAG), the International Space Exploration Coordination Group (ISECG), and the Inter-Agency Space Debris Coordinating Committee (IADC); Artemis Accords signatories meetings; ILRS (coordination information not public); within standards organizations such as ISO; within advisory or technical coordination groups such as the Lunar Surface Innovation Consortium (LSIC) and Lunar Exploration Analysis Group (LEAG); through voluntarily participation in NASA's MADCAP conjunction assessment service; and terms set by programme requirements or by contract (including between nongov-

ernmental actors), in addition to nationally developed laws, regulations, and guidelines. The influence of each of these groups in shaping future lunar behavior surrounding the mitigation of interference is highly dependent on which actors become dominant in lunar activity and their motivation.

We examine the following scenarios:

1. Chinese crewed landing and ILRS permanently inhabited prior to establishment of permanently inhabited Artemis station
2. Artemis and ILRS concurrent progress
3. Development of economically viable commercial lunar market driven by robotic exploration
4. Commercial monopoly or duopoly in the majority of lunar activities (e.g., SpaceX and/or Blue Origin)
5. Public-private coalition led activity, with collective investment in lunar infrastructure.

Regardless of scenario, establishing baseline transparency and confidence-building measures are critical to ensure the mitigation of interference. This may include the sharing of information during mission development, the sharing of lessons learned post-mission, establishing bilateral coordination procedures for realtime deconfliction, the sharing of scientific data, improvement of interoperability standards, establishing additional formal or informal grievance mechanisms, public consultations, and more. The efficacy of each of these mechanisms is highly dependent on the dominant lunar actors, as well as broader geopolitical considerations (e.g., elevated U.S./China tensions decreasing transparency at large). We highlight interference coordination needs and the relative strengths of the mapped institutions in meeting these needs, as well as gaps or shortcomings, in potential futures.

[1] T. Jones (2025), "U.S. Space Policymaking in a New Era of Commercialization", RAND Corporation, https://www.rand.org/content/dam/rand/pubs/rgs_dissertations/RGSDA4200/RGSDA4235-1/RAND_RGSDA4235-1.pdf